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MODERN METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS AND MALIGNANT TUMORS

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Abstract

The coexistence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis significantly complicates diagnosis and treatment, leading to increased morbidity and mortality rates. Effective management of these comorbid conditions requires a comprehensive approach involving modern diagnostic and treatment methods. This article explores the clinical features of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis co-occurrence, challenges in accurate diagnosis, and the latest diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. It provides recommendations for healthcare professionals to identify and treat these diseases effectively. The study aims to improve practical skills in the early detection, accurate diagnosis, and successful management of these comorbid conditions.

Keywords

- Malignant tumors
- Pulmonary tuberculosis
- Comorbidity
- Diagnosis challenges
- Clinical features
- Treatment

Relevance

Malignant tumors (MT) and pulmonary tuberculosis (PT) are among the most critical health issues globally, characterized by high mortality rates and treatment challenges. The comorbidity of these diseases, i.e., their simultaneous occurrence, presents a complex and pressing issue in clinical practice. Immunosuppression caused by MT predisposes patients to PT, complicating the clinical course of both diseases and posing significant difficulties in diagnosis and treatment.

Patients with MT are more susceptible to developing PT due to weakened immune systems. This increases morbidity and mortality rates and complicates

clinical diagnosis due to overlapping symptoms and increased risk of complications. Standard tuberculosis treatment protocols may interact with cancer treatment drugs, requiring a personalized treatment approach.

Comorbidity of MT and PT poses significant diagnostic challenges because of the overlapping clinical features and radiological findings. Therefore, comprehensive clinical, laboratory, and instrumental studies are necessary to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective treatment.

This research is highly relevant to healthcare professionals in understanding the interaction between malignant tumors and tuberculosis, enabling them to devise effective diagnostic and treatment strategies. It will enhance clinicians' ability to detect, diagnose, and manage these diseases effectively.

Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the clinical characteristics of the comorbid occurrence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis, identify diagnostic challenges, and develop effective diagnostic and treatment methods.

Materials and Methods

Study Type and Subjects: This study examined comorbid patients with malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis diagnosed between 2022 and 2020. Clinical data from over 100 patients were analyzed, including 80 patients with MT and 40 patients with PT. The most common cancer types were lung, stomach, liver, and breast cancers, with pulmonary tuberculosis primarily in the pulmonary form.

Age, gender, medical history, and initial disease symptoms were documented through a structured survey. General patient information, clinical symptoms, disease duration, and comorbidity characteristics were studied.

Results

Patients with malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis showed distinct clinical courses, revealing challenges in diagnosis and treatment. The study identified unique clinical signs, diagnostic difficulties, and therapeutic complexities due to the coexistence of both diseases. Cancer patients showed higher susceptibility to tuberculosis due to compromised immune systems, and their simultaneous occurrence complicated clinical symptoms.

The findings emphasized that combined treatment strategies are required. However, side effects and drug interactions between anti-tuberculosis and chemotherapy agents necessitate individualized treatment approaches.

Conclusion

1. Comorbid Disease Characteristics: The comorbidity of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis presents unique clinical challenges, with overlapping symptoms complicating diagnosis.

2. Diagnosis Challenges: Simultaneous occurrence of these diseases requires comprehensive laboratory and instrumental examinations for accurate diagnosis.

3. Treatment Strategies: Combined treatment strategies involving anti-tuberculosis and cancer therapies are necessary. Individualized treatment plans should consider potential drug interactions and side effects.

4. Recommendations:

- Routine screening for comorbid conditions should be implemented.
- Clinicians should adopt individualized approaches in managing MT and T.
 - Training programs should enhance clinicians' knowledge and skills in managing these comorbidities.

This study provides clinicians with a comprehensive understanding of diagnosing and treating the coexistence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis, improving healthcare professionals' practical skills and contributing to better patient outcomes.

References:

1. Mashrabovna I. I., Faxriddinova N. D. Modern method of differential diagnosis tuberculosis and lung cancer //Sci. J. Med. Res. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 21-30.
2. Ismoilovich A. F. Tuberculosis Diagnostics with Modern Solutions (Literature Review) //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 377-383.
3. Ulugbek o'gli A. M. Factors Predicting Mortality in Pulmonary Tuberculosis //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 362-367.
4. Ilkhomovna K. D. Morphological Features of Tumor in Different Treatment Options for Patients with Locally Advanced Breast Cancer //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 4-5.
5. Khodzhaeva D. I. Changes in the Vertebral Column and Thoracic Spine cells after Postponement of Mastectomy //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 109-113.

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